

SOME THOUGHTS ON THE IMPORTANCE AND HISTORY OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE IN WORLD LANGUAGES

Sharipov Bobur Salimovich

Assistant teacher Department of Languages, Samarkand State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10029879>

Abstract: This article discusses the importance and history of the Latin language in today's world languages. It always shows the importance and weight of the Latin language in today's communication. In this regard, it is noteworthy that the terms of all fields, regardless of the language in which they are used, are not used in that language, but in Latin.

Keywords: Archaic Latin, syntactic development, humanism, transformation, communication.

НЕКОТОРЫЕ МЫСЛИ О ВАЖНОСТИ И ИСТОРИИ ЛАТИНСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В МИРОВЫХ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение и история латинского языка в современных мировых языках. Это всегда показывает важность и вес латинского языка в современном общении. В связи с этим примечательно, что термины всех полей, независимо от языка, на котором они используются, используются не на этом языке, а на латинице.

Ключевые слова: архаическая латынь, синтаксическое развитие, гуманизм, трансформация, общение.

INTRODUCTION

Latin (or simply "Latin"), one of the oldest Indo-European languages, belongs to the Latin-Faliscan subgroup of the Italic languages of the Indo-European language family. Today it is the only Italian language actively used, despite the fact that Latin is considered a dead language. Dead languages are languages that do not have living speakers. There have been no people for whom Latin was their native language for more than one and a half thousand years.

In the history of the development of the Latin language, several stages can be distinguished (the article uses Western periodization): Archaic Latin. It covers the period up to 75 BC. The oldest written monument in Latin that has reached us is the so-called "Duenos inscription", which very vaguely resembles the Latin language in the modern sense. At the beginning of the first millennium BC, the Latin language was used by the population of the Latium region (Latium in Latin).

MAIN PART

This area was located in the middle part of the Apennine Peninsula. The people who inhabited this area were called "Latins", and the language they spoke was "Latin". The center of the Latium region, the city of Rome, eventually became the capital of a powerful state. Classical Latin. This stage covers the period from 75 BC. until approximately 200 after the birth of Christ. The concept of "classical Latin" is applied, as a rule, to the literary Latin language, which has reached a high level of its morphological and syntactic development. The works of Cicero, Caesar, Virgil, Horace and Ovid are considered to be examples of "classical Latin". This is the period of Rome's transformation into the largest slave-owning state, subjugating vast territories. Classical Latin was the language of educated citizens of the Roman Empire. At the same time, what we understand by "classical Latin" is, in fact, a stylized written literary language.

The language spoken by the people of the Roman Empire is "vulgar Latin" (or "folk Latin"). It is folk Latin that is the direct ancestor of the Romance languages. Medieval Latin (300

– 1300). This medieval form of Latin was common in Western Europe for business and educational purposes, and as a liturgical language. For many centuries, this form of Latin was the main means of interlingual communication in church life, government, school, science and diplomacy. Latin of the Renaissance (1300 - 1600). The ideological basis of the Renaissance was humanism, the main content of which was the cult of man, placed at the center of the universe. According to this ideology, antiquity is an ideal historical period in which science and art, the state and society flourished. Writers sought to imitate ancient models, especially the language of Cicero. During the Renaissance, the Latin language became the most important means of scientific and cultural communication. New Latin (1600 – 1900). The term "New Latin" came into use in the late 19th century to refer to the form of Latin after the end of the Renaissance. During this period, Latin was a compulsory subject in all European schools, and universities required applicants to know Latin.

New Latin was the language of interlingual communication in Catholic and Protestant countries of Europe, as well as in many colonies. Legal, diplomatic, scientific and educational documents were written in Latin, since text not written in Latin could be understood only by a small number of people, while Latin text could always and everywhere be translated. Lomonosov, Spinoza, Newton and many others wrote their works in Latin. Latin was the official language in the parliaments of some countries (for example, in Hungary until 1848). Modern Latin (since 1900). Modern Latin is the form of the Latin language used from the early 20th century to the present. By the beginning of the 20th century, Latin had virtually disappeared from use, with the exception of some specialized areas where it is used as nomenclature:

- Anatomical nomenclature.
- International veterinary anatomical nomenclature.
- International Code of Zoological Nomenclature.
- International Code of Botanical Nomenclature.
- International Code of Nomenclature of Bacteria. The reasons for the displacement of Latin are varied:
 - Growth of national self-awareness, increased interest in national culture and national language. The Latin language was replaced by national languages.
 - The priority role of the French language since the beginning of the 19th century due to the leading role of France in the world political arena.
 - Growing interest in the study of foreign languages, understanding of the fact that the Latin language is nothing more than an intermediary language, which can be completely dispensed with.
 - Isolation of the educational process in Latin in schools from modern problems, since the educational process was built exclusively on classical texts of the Roman period.

The movement for the use of Latin in modern life emerged in the early 20th century as an attempt at cultural revival based on the rich traditions of antiquity and in line with movements seeking to achieve a more integrated Europe. An example was the revival of Hebrew, a dead language that was previously used exclusively as the language of liturgy and written sources. The language, which was considered extinct for 18 centuries, has become the spoken language and official language of the State of Israel. Recently, there has been an increasing trend towards the activation of the Latin language. This movement was called "Latinitas viva" ("Living Latin"). Congresses of Living Latin are held in many countries. As an example, we can name Germany, where the society "Societas Latina" was created, the center of which is located in Saarbrücken.

The "Latinitas viva" movement also promotes the revival of spoken Latin. There are a number of purely linguistic problems here. If Latin grammar remained virtually unchanged for

centuries, the phonetic design of spoken Latin speech, and, most importantly, the search for Latin equivalents for new concepts that did not, and could not have existed, during the time of the Roman Empire, pose difficult problems. In the field of phonetics, the struggle is between “Italian” (or “church”) and “classical” pronunciation.

And although the positions of the first option are supported by the texts of classical music, Catholic liturgy, and the use of Latin as the official language in the Vatican, the “classical” pronunciation undoubtedly wins, since it is traditionally used in many countries. There are many different points of view in the area of introducing new Latin vocabulary. The priority here belongs to the Vatican - over the past seven years, 15 leading experts have translated more than 15,000 new words into Latin (for example, “car muffler” - tubulus emmissarius, “egg liqueur” - merum ovo infusum). But although the Vatican regularly publishes dictionaries of new vocabulary, they are not accepted and used unconditionally.

CONCLUSION

Many Latin neologisms are rather cumbersome descriptions, for example: “vodka” - valida potio Slavica (literally: a strong Slavic drink), “basketball” - follis canistrigue ludus (literally: a game with a ball and a basket). The dictionary of modern Latin vocabulary published by the Vatican is called “Lexicon recentis Latinitatis”. It exists in many national variants.

To say that Latin can eventually regain its position as the international language of science and culture is hardly true today. But the fact that the Latin language will live and develop in accordance with the needs of our time is an indisputable fact. This is confirmed by the fact that Pope Benedict XVI publicly calls for the development of Latin and the involvement of young people in its study.

LITERATURES:

1. Mukhamadiyeva, M., & Sharipov, B. (2022). LATIN AS THE MAIN LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(7), 337-339.
2. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.
3. Sharipov, B. (2022). RETSIPROKLIK XUSUSIDA MULOHAZALAR. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 1(19), 63-66.
4. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). RECIPROCAL SYMMETRY AND ITS GRAMMATICAL INDICATIONS. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(12), 129-131.
5. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). Studies of Reciprocity in Linguistics. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 8, 221-224.
6. Isroilova, M., & Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME OBSERVATIONS ON LATIN PRONUNCIATION AND SPELLING. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(7), 127-129.
7. Шарипов, Б. С. (2022). TIL BIRLIKLARINING NUTQDA FAOLLASHUVI HAQIDA. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(1).
8. Nasimjanovna, K. F., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). NAMES OF DISEASES AND THEIR USE IN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 469-474.

9. Salimovich, S. B. (2022, January). FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE UNITS. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 62-63).
10. Mardanovich, M. Z., Aliaskarovna, S. U., Kenjaevna, B. M., Genjebaevna, A. P., & Salimovich, S. B. (2021). Some Considerations about Legal Solutions and Practices of Certain Problems Writing Recipes. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 5341-5352.
11. ZAFAR, M., BOBUR, S., & DILMUROD, B. R. (2021). Scientific and pedagogical basis of teaching the theory of decisions in school chemistry. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 192-196.
12. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). The role of teaching latin in the course of subject training of future foreign language teachers. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 11-14.
13. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Features of teaching latin to students medical universities studying in english. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 21-25.
14. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Influence of the latin language on the formation of medical terminology. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 16-20.
15. Maxmudov, Z., Sharipov, B., & Bo'riyev, D. (2023). Tibbiyot universitetlarida lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 5-10.
16. Maxmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. (2021). LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 1028-1033.
17. Maxmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR.
18. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Developing Students Attitudes Towards the Environment When Teaching a Foreign Languages. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 199-201.
19. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Reviews of effective use of educational methods in teaching latin and medical terminology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 381-386.
20. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).
21. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. (2022, August). AUDITORIYADAN TASHQARI TA'LIM-TARBIYAGA MAQSADLI, TIZIMLI YONDASHISH:

Mahmudov Zafar Mardanovich Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti, Tillar kafedrası, assistent, e-mail: maxmudovzafar4510@ gmail. com Sharipov Bobur Salimovich Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti, Tillar kafedrası, assistent, e-mail: sharipovbobur9689@ gmail. com Bo'riyev Dilmurod Arzimurodovich Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti, Tillar kafedrası, stajyor-assistent buriyev. d0905@ gmail. com. In *Научно-практическая конференция*.

22. Maxmudov, Z. M. (2021). Bobur Salimovich Sharipov Lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning didaktik tamoyillari va uning asosi haqida fikrlar. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 6.